

THE IMPORTANCE OF COOPERATION BETWEEN PRESCHOOL AND SCHOOL

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Abstract: In this article, changes occur in the child's body and psychology during the transition from kindergarten to school education. It begins the period of adaptation. In this process, the child faces a number of difficulties. The process of passing the game makes it difficult for the child to perceive the learning process himself. In these cases, the cooperation between parents and the preschool educational institution is very important, and the creation of a common educational environment between the preschool educational organization and the school is one of the factors affecting the adaptation of the elementary school student in the society. About the continuity of kindergarten and school work, the problem of adapting the first grader to new educational conditions and the role of child psychologists, teachers, doctors and scientists in this field occupy a special place in solving this problem the word goes.

Key words: Game, education, adaptation, adaptation, cooperation, game activity, learning activity, environment.

The cooperation between the preschool education organization and the school ensures that the children are sent to school with knowledge that meets the requirements of school education, and that they are generally developed and educated, and that the teacher, based on the knowledge, skills and qualities of school-age children, and creates a basis for use in educational processes.

During the transition from kindergarten to school education, changes occur in the child's body and psychology. It begins the period of adaptation. In this process, the child faces a number of difficulties. The process of passing the game makes it difficult for the child to perceive the learning process himself. In these cases, cooperation between parents and the preschool educational institution is very important, and it is necessary to create a common educational environment between the preschool educational organization and the school. The main goal of educational organizations in creating such a unified educational environment is the reasonable development of a unified approach to education and upbringing issues.

It is necessary to develop and put into practice the draft normative document regulating the cooperation between the preschool education

organization and the school, and on the basis of this norm, organize the activities of the kindergarten and the school according to the work plan of mutual cooperation. Since this activity is planned and carried out directly with pedagogical staff, analytical and practical activities, seminars and conferences are carried out through joint pedagogical readings and thematic pedagogical halls. It is recommended to plan and conduct mutual visits of teachers and classes. This gives teachers the opportunity to focus on the difficulties children face and to plan future learning activities taking into account the identified problems. In addition, organizing excursions to educational institutions, organizing meetings with experienced elementary school teachers is an effective way to prepare children for school education. Also, during this cooperation, the process of children's adaptation from the kindergarten environment to the school environment will be separately controlled, analyzed, and the children's adaptation process will be guided by the traffic light method, and the children with red indicators will be dealt with individually and they will be adapted to school education. ``consent is required. The following are important in the cooperation between the school and the preschool education organization. Based on the knowledge, skills and qualities acquired by the teacher of school-age children, it creates a basis for use in lessons and educational processes.

The leading activity of a preschool child is a game. The development of the main psychological processes - memory, attention, attention, thinking, imagination.

Forms of behavior acquired by children of preschool education age, forms of interaction with adults and peers, moral feelings and imaginations are the basis for educating children in the elementary grades of new moral behavior, mind, and feelings. serves as Based on the requirements of school education, children should acquire knowledge more deeply, children should be mentally prepared for school, activities conducted in pre-school education organization should be in a developmental way, children should be interested in mental work.

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